

**ENCOURAGING STUDENTS' ACTIVITIES THROUGH INTERACTIVE
TEACHING METHODS IN SPECIAL SUBJECT CLASSES****Gulnoza Mirzakhmatovna Anarkulova**Professor, Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences
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This article describes the essence of pedagogical technologies and methods for teaching specialized subjects in higher education institutions. Examples of the use of interactive teaching methods in specialized subject classes are provided.

Keywords: higher education, pedagogical technologies, specialized disciplines, teaching method, interactive methods.

The 21st century is the age of technology, and modern technologies have rapidly permeated all aspects of society, including the educational process at all levels of the lifelong learning system. The application of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive innovative learning technologies in higher education requires special responsibility from every participant in the educational process.

In the 1960s, the education system underwent a dramatic shift, which was called the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the educational process.

Educational scientists from all over the world did not ignore this process. Every educator began to develop and implement modern educational technologies that could be incorporated into the educational process.

As a result of extensive research, the following educational scientists put forward their theories, including the development of technological approaches to the organization of learning by Yu.K. Babansky, V.P. Bepalko, N.F. Talyzina, L.M. Fridman, Yu.N. Kulyutkin, G.S. Sukhobskaya, T.V. Kudryavtsev, A.M. Matyushkina, M.I. Makhmutova were of great significance. [2]

An analysis of technological approaches shows that many educational technologies remain weakly technological. Some technologies are dominated by theoretical foundations, while the activity-based aspect is not entirely concrete.

The problem of pedagogical technologies contains many unanswered questions. Research into this issue is related to the definition of the concept and methodological essence of educational technologies.

In defining the essence of pedagogical technologies, educational scholars have put forward their own definitions.

B. Likhachev provides the following definition: "Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical principles that determine a specific set and arrangement of forms, methods, techniques, and educational tools; it is the organizational and methodological toolkit of the pedagogical process."

"Pedagogical technology is a substantive technique for implementing the educational process" (V.P. Bepalko).[3]

"Pedagogical technology is a description of the process of achieving planned learning outcomes" (I.P. Volkov).

"Technology is an art, a skill, a skill, a set of methods for processing and changing a state" (V.M. Shepel).

"Pedagogical technology is a well-thought-out model of joint pedagogical activity for the design, organization, and implementation of the educational process, with the unconditional provision of comfortable conditions for students and teachers" (V.M. Monakhov).

"Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying, and defining the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human resources and their interaction, with the goal of optimizing educational forms" (UNESCO).

"Pedagogical technology means the systemic set and order of functioning of all personal, instrumental, and methodological means used to achieve pedagogical goals" (M.V. Klarin).

"Pedagogical technology is a substantive generalization that incorporates the meanings of all definitions from various authors (sources)" (G.K. Selevko). [2]

An analysis of these definitions shows that pedagogical technology is understood as the planning and application within the framework of education of a system of means for achieving the desired result.

Teaching technology refers to a theoretical design for pedagogical management of educational activities and a system of necessary resources that ensure the functioning of the teaching system in accordance with the stated educational goals and student development.

Reforms in higher education require a scientifically based approach to the implementation of teaching technology in the educational process.

Not all design, being a means of scientifically substantiating teaching, is technological.

The primary goal of teaching technology is the achievement of the goals of the educational process and personal development. The specificity of teaching technology in the context of designing a teaching system for higher education institutions lies in the interaction between teacher and students. It is important to keep in mind that design is not limited to distinguishing between teaching systems or individual components of these systems.

Design serves a methodological function. It serves as a means of studying the patterns of students' mental development, the characteristics of the formation of learning activities, and methods of teaching management. Throughout the history of the formation and development of the subject of pedagogy, the concept of pedagogical technology has been interpreted in various ways, ranging from the initial interpretation as teaching through technical means to the concept of pedagogical technology as the systematic and consistent organization of a designed learning process. Currently, there are a number of definitions of pedagogical technology.

V.P. Bepalko defines pedagogical technology as the design of a specific pedagogical system as the basis for developing the technology. In this formulation, V.P. Bepalko advocates the need for process design. However, the concepts of "pedagogical technology" or "project" are unclear. [3]

Despite the fact that pedagogical technologies are invading the educational process, their status remains uncertain. As research shows, pedagogical technologies occupy an intermediate position between science and practice.

N.F. Talyzina believes that every teacher, before constructing a real pedagogical process, must have a system of knowledge about the educational process, represented at the technological level. [2]

In higher education institutions, several types of educational organization are defined for the teaching of specialized disciplines, including the following: lectures, seminars and practical classes, laboratory work, educational conferences, consultations, excursions, expeditions, practical training, coursework and theses, and independent student research. If the organizational forms of this educational process are determined based on the curriculum, each teacher can choose the organizational forms of classes based on the objectives of the lesson.

When organizing training in specialized disciplines in higher education, the use of modular teaching technologies and an approach based on the specifics of the subject contributes

to the effectiveness of the specialist training system.

Organizing instruction using modular learning technologies requires the instructor to carefully develop a lesson plan. A lesson plan is a methodological tool that defines the order of learning stages over a specific period of time. To enhance learning effectiveness, the use of interactive teaching methods, along with reproductive and productive learning methods, is also important.

Interactive methods are teaching methods in which the instructor, student, and group of students actively participate in the joint achievement of educational goals.

Interactive teaching methods include: the learning contract method, the educational project method, case studies, small group work, synchronization, the "black box" method, the "boomerang" method, game technologies, business games, entrepreneurship games, brainstorming, roundtable discussions, the "snowstorm" method, the "6-6" method, and others.

Here are a few examples of using the above-mentioned interactive teaching methods in specialized subject lessons.

The "Learning Contract" method is more suited for use in seminars. For a seminar-training session, a "Learning Contract" is written on a flipchart. This means that the students themselves develop rules for the seminar-training participants. (For example: arrive on time, don't be late, participants should not share each other's opinions, maintain mutual respect, and similar rules.)

After signing the contract, all participants express their agreement and sign the "contract"—a flipchart.

In some cases of contract violation, various interesting punishments can be prepared. For example, a participant who violates the contract will be required to recite a poem or song. This will provide a lyrical digression from the topic of the seminar-training and will help lift the participants' spirits.

It is advisable to hang the "Learning Contract" in a location in the room where the participants can see it during the seminar.

Role-playing is used in situations involving the discussion of a specific issue, problem, situation, or task related to the training topic and the decision-making process. It should be noted that each participant is assigned a specific role.

Training sessions using this method enhance the level of preparation for practical work by having participants perform their assigned roles in specific settings and situations. In this case, participants' participation in various roles not only makes the training more engaging but

also helps achieve the objectives.

For example, during a practical training session with economists, students are divided into several subgroups. Each group plays specific roles, such as bank employees, clients arriving at a designated location, or observers. This allows for observation of actual financial transactions conducted at the bank.

In general, there are various forms of role-playing. Examples include "Aquarium," "Mirror," "Role Duplication," "Parallel," "Role Exchange," "Role Rotation," and "Chair Interview."

The 6-6 Method: A group of at least six people spends six minutes formulating a specific idea that will help solve the group's problem. Each participant writes down their thoughts on separate sheets of paper. This is done very briefly: in the form of a coherence analysis, materials analysis, or technology analysis. All prepared lists are then discussed as a group.

During the discussion, extreme misconceptions are eliminated, controversial issues are clarified, and all remaining identified features are grouped. The goal is to select a few important alternatives, so their number can be small compared to the number of participants.

The Brainstorming Method. The purpose of this method is to collect as many ideas as possible, free students from the inertia of monotonous thinking, and teach them creative tasks. This method was recommended by A.F. Osborn, and its main goal and rule is not to criticize the ideas expressed by students, but to embrace all thoughts and ideas. Any jokes and anecdotes related to the topic should be encouraged. When using this method, the teacher should actively encourage each student to express ideas. When using the "Brainstorming" method, all students in the lesson should contribute their ideas. [3]

Student learning should be consciously aimed at achieving learning goals, which are perceived as personal essence. D.B. Elkonin emphasizes that learning is, first and foremost, an activity that results in change within the student. The activity itself may be the change, but its product is a change in the form of intrinsic motivation that arises within the student. [5]

Thus, the use of interactive teaching methods in higher education helps students develop skills in using various types and styles of communication, while simultaneously developing their communicative and creative thinking. This, in turn, leads to increased educational effectiveness.

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